

Report on the Focus Group

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COVER PAGE

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DISCLAIMER

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ACRONYMS

Acronym	Full name
AP	Associated Partner
BEN	Beneficiary
CA	Consortium Agreement
CM	Communication Manager
CO/OM	Coordinator/Operational Manager
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FM	Financial Manager
GA	Grant Agreement
GAs	General Assembly
PC	Project Coordinator
PMT	Project Management Team
QA	Quality Assurance
QAM	Quality Assurance Manager
QAP	Quality Assurance Plan
RP	Reporting Period
SAB	Scientific Advisory Board
TL	Task Leader
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader
WT	Working Tasks

1. REPORT ON THE FOCUS GROUP ON THE THEME: “SUSTAINABILITY AND SUSTAINABILITY REPORTING”

In the focus group on the theme: “Sustainability and Sustainability Reporting” 24 participants took part. Their characteristics are as follows:

1. Expertise Structure:

○ *The expertise structure of the participants covers several areas such as follows:*

- sustainability, workplace safety and health, as well as product safety,
- education in sustainable development and environmental protection,
- managing operations in green business companies as well as in other industries (cement industry),
- consulting and training of the companies and financial institutions in the process of establishing the ESG concept,
- scientific research regarding the environment, construction, energy, and other natural and social sciences
- project management,
- managing different kind of departments.

2. Positions:

○ The participants hold different positions in their organisations, which include the following:

- managers in the fields of sustainability, workplace safety and health, product safety, project management, law, and financial management,
- managers in non-governmental organisations from the civil society sector concerned with nature conservation and combating the negative impacts of climate change,
- directors of operations, credit risk sector, recycling industry, cement company,
- head of the process management department,
- assistant director of the credit risk sector,
- policy advisor on climate change, environment, and air quality,
- analyst and specialist for sustainable business,
- scientific researcher,
- university teacher.

3. Gender:

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The participants in the focus group were selected due to their experience in areas such as sustainability management, supervision in the field of environmental protection and workplace safety and health, education on the importance of sustainable business practices, and sustainability reporting. consulting services and training to companies and financial institutions in the process of establishing the ESG etc. Accordingly, all participants were able to provide informed opinions on the discussed topic.

To gain deeper insights into the significance of sustainability and sustainability reporting, participants were asked questions divided into several areas: (I) Environmental, economic, and social aspects of sustainability; (II) Areas where the widening countries lag behind other countries in terms of sustainability; (III) Circular economy activities applicable in widening countries; (IV) Opportunities for using information technology to support sustainability; and (V) Sustainability reporting practices in the widening countries, as well as potentials and limitations in this area.

(I) Environmental, economic, and social aspects of sustainability

The first group of questions referred to the environmental aspects of sustainability and environmental problems that are present in the widening countries. It was also related to the impact of climate change and changes in the environment on the business activities of the companies. In addition, some questions referred to the economic and social aspects of sustainability.

When it comes to ***the environmental aspects*** of sustainability, all of the participants agreed that in this area there are many challenges. One of the problems that participants pointed out was the insufficient use of renewable energy sources. However, they also pointed out that the existence of wind generators and solar power plants at the present moment is not enough to ensure a safe supply of electricity to the economy. Therefore, relying on traditional sources of energy (thermal power plants) in the current stage of the development of our economy is necessary, but that does not mean that we should not go in the direction of using renewable energy sources.

One of the most significant problems in the field of ecology, as identified by the respondents, is water pollution as well. In many cases, companies discharge wastewater into rivers without purification plants.

The next problem that was identified regarding the ecological aspects of sustainability are the problems regarding recycling. Generally, the recycling industry is not well developed, either in terms of practices for collecting waste. Also, the participant mentioned that the problem with the utilisation and recycling of waste is that larger amounts of waste are needed to economically justify its recycling.

The participant also emphasised the problem of illegal landfills and expressed the view that large projects for recycling and solving illegal landfills are needed. Several participants agreed that, although solid and liquid waste is a problem, it has great potential that companies could use for ecological sustainability and economic benefits.

The participants also highlighted the importance of the banking sector in promoting environmental practices. In that context, it was stated that in some banks, almost 20% of the loan portfolio is green. In addition, more and more banks do not support financing activities related to the exploitation and use of coal due to CO₂ emissions, increasing crediting for projects in the area of renewable energy sources (investments in solar panels and mini hydropower plants) in the last two years, and financing projects in the area of energy-efficient housing.

Also, there are organisations that participate in spreading awareness and knowledge about the ESG concept by providing consulting services and training to companies, financial institutions, and business associations in B&H in the process of establishing the ESG concept.

Regarding this topic, it was also pointed out that it is necessary to work on the education of young people in order to become aware of the importance of ecological aspects of sustainability even in childhood. However, education in this area should continue during further education, which also requires the active involvement of the academic community.

When asked **whether climate changes** have caused certain consequences for the operations of companies whose representatives are participants in the focus group, the participants stated that they have observed both positive and negative impacts. The *positive* impact is reflected in the fact that savings in energy consumption are achieved during the winter, while the *negative* impact is manifested in the summer in the form of increased consumption of electricity for cooling devices.

When it comes to **the economic impact of** sustainable practices, the respondents agree that they have the potential to bring economic benefits to companies' operations. It was also concluded that companies should accept sustainable practices as an inevitable part of their existence and integrate them into their business strategies to ensure competitiveness and success in the long term. In short, sustainable practices should be integrated into the company's business model.

From the aspect of banking, the economic effect of sustainability is reflected in better access to financial resources for companies as a basic need for business development. On the other hand, savings resulting from using renewable resources at the same time protect the environment and have the potential to improve the financial results of companies, too.

Some of the respondents regarding the economic effects of sustainability pointed out that the primary benefit of sustainable practices is attracting investment and finances, as well as saving resources. The participants also see the possibility of attracting new business and new buyers from the EU after the application of the concepts of sustainability and reporting.

The economic effects of sustainability, in addition to profitability, also included the importance of the image and reputation of companies. The participants expressed confidence that sustainable practices can have a positive effect on the image of companies, which can increase the trust and loyalty of customers and investors.

However, participants addressed several obstacles to gaining understanding of the economic effects of sustainability practices. For example, the respondents pointed to the problem that certain types of waste, in the absence of appropriate recycling infrastructure in the country, have to be exported to large centres in Europe, which significantly increases the cost of the recycling process. In addition, it was pointed out that responsible companies, when importing electronic devices, pay the eco tax, while other companies avoid this tax by classifying the imported devices in the "other" category, for which no taxes are paid. In this way, they become more competitive in price compared to responsible companies. Further, sustainable practices have a higher and faster return for businesses than households, although some participants emphasised that the economic benefits of solar panels are not as good as advertised in the promotion of the production of solar energy since the payback period is not 5–6 years as initially promoted, but 10–11 years. However, in some countries, this period is much shorter.

The banking industry also sees economic effects from a higher degree of digitalization.

The next issue that was discussed was **the social aspects of sustainability**. All of the participants in the focus group pointed out that their companies are very committed to this issue and that they

apply numerous practices that are aimed both at the well-being of employees and at a positive impact on the wider social community. Commitment to the social aspects of sustainability of some companies whose representatives were participants in the focus group resulted in certain certificates confirming that they are socially responsible, such as a certificate on respecting the equality of men and women based on earnings, development, and advancement, as well as for different groups and populations, and a certificate as a top employer.

The banking industry also has many good examples of social responsibility. Their contribution is also seen in organising training for financial and non-financial institutions in the area of sustainability and energy efficiency. In addition, representatives from the banking industry emphasised that their organisation does not finance certain industries that are not ecologically and socially responsible. The other participant from the banking sector confirmed that the banking sector is increasingly investing in green products and issuing green bonds.

The representatives from the banking sector pointed out that banks started raising awareness for environmental and social issues long before it was articulated by the local regulators, due to the orientation of the international financial market. However, it is valuable to have a private sector that operates according to environmental and social regulations.

Regarding this topic, respondents stated that although there are bright examples of companies that are committed to social responsibility, there are still challenges in this area. In that direction, the respondent from the non-governmental organisation emphasised that nowadays, "the eco should replace the ego," underscoring the necessary need to change the system of values. In addition, it was also stressed that companies should devote themselves to creating social value, not just to marketing and financial gain.

As a main obstacle in the implementation of socially responsible behaviour, the respondents highlighted the lack of legal regulation, the danger of unwanted practices such as social washing, which occurs if sustainability is understood only as marketing, and the need for more creative ways of identifying vulnerable groups in the community for targeting social sustainability activities. The challenges highlighted by the respondents also included measuring the social aspect of companies' sustainability. According to them, measuring environmental impact is relatively easy compared to measuring social aspects, such as gender balance in the work environment and workforce diversity.

II - The aspect of sustainability that is the least developed in the widening countries and key problems in the implementation of sustainable practices.

The second group of questions was aimed at identifying the least developed aspect of sustainability as well as addressing the key problems/challenges in implementing sustainable practices in companies.

According to the opinions of the respondents, the least developed aspect of sustainability is different in different countries. In some widening countries, the respondents stated that it was the *environmental aspect*, while in others it was the social aspect. However, the respondents agree that all aspects of sustainability are connected. It was also pointed out that investments in environmental aspects of sustainability are considered a cost in most cases, but that they are, in fact, an investment in the future. Discussing this topic, some of the respondents pointed out that companies have an obligation to adjust polluting emissions by 2025, but currently no one is dealing with it. The

respondents suggested that the transition to renewable energy sources should be systematic, proposing a deadline for the closure of thermal power plants and starting the retraining of workers who would lose their jobs due to this.

There is also a suggestion to raise awareness among the companies about the importance of protecting the rivers. The respondents stated that there are not enough wastewater treatment plants. They also pointed out that if their construction has been started, their completion is delayed, and if they are even built, they are not used.

In addition, respondents pointed out that sustainability still has no value in the market, in the sense that a sustainable business should be preferred compared to a less sustainable or not sustainable business at all. In other words, there is no evaluation system for businesses regarding this aspect. For this reason, an awareness or information campaign is needed for customers in this regard. Until now, when there has been no such assessment, the competition between businesses has been unfair. For companies that work with foreign clients, this part is easier because they understand the value of sustainability.

As for the obstacle to implementing the social aspect of sustainability, the respondents address that it is “much more difficult to measure and requires more awareness and knowledge in this area” than in other aspects of sustainability.

Other obstacles that have been identified are the absence of appropriate recycling infrastructure, causing some companies to have to export waste to large centres in Europe, which significantly increases the cost of the recycling process.

In general, the following challenges are listed as ***the challenges of implementing sustainable practices*** in widening countries:

1. non-implementation of legal regulations,
2. non-existence of legal regulations that more closely regulate certain areas,
3. the gap between the needs of the economy and legal regulations,
4. bureaucratic or administrative obstacles related to obtaining various permits,
5. lack of infrastructure that enables waste recycling,
6. low awareness among people about the importance of sustainability.

III - Circular Economy

The third group of questions focused on whether, in the business models of the organisations of the participants, the circular economy is implemented, as well as the activities of the circular economy that can be applied in their countries.

The respondents stressed that the essence of the circular economy is to increase the productivity of resources and to create a closed loop in which resources are returned to use, thereby reducing pressure on the environment. They also pointed out that recycling is not a circular economy but only one link in the chain.

The respondents from widening countries argue that the activities of the circular economy in their country are very few, and only some large enterprises can follow them. They also added that

implementing the practices of circular economy activities in small and medium enterprises is quite impossible.

Although recycling is only one of the activities in the circular economy, the authorities did not pay sufficient attention to this issue. As an example, it was noted that in some widening countries at the level of the (municipal) waste collection sector, the waste collection rate is around 20 to 30%, which is less than what informal waste pickers collect. The respondent also noted weaknesses in the deposit-refund system, which should be established in a more comprehensive and accessible manner. In comparison, one of the respondents shared that deposit-refund systems have a success rate of over 80% in other countries.

In order for the practices of the circular economy to be advanced, the respondents recommended better legal solutions for the circular economy, the promotion of cooperation, and the establishment of a special system for the collection and management of special types of waste.

IV - Possibilities of applying information technology as a support for sustainability practices.

The fourth group of questions referred on the possibilities for the application of IT as support for sustainability practices.

All respondents agreed that the possibilities for applying IT to the function of sustainability are numerous. The respondents stated that IT can be used in the spheres of production automation, optimisation of business processes in order to save energy, etc. In addition, artificial intelligence can be used for data reduction, waste sorting (especially in the field of e-recycling), processing large amounts of data, etc.

The participants from the banking sector mentioned the digitalization of a large number of services and the use of mobile banking, which, as a consequence, reduces the need for physical visits to the bank, thereby reducing the number of branches and ATMs that are ecologically "dirty." They also mentioned the problem and obstacle of using IT solutions due to their high cost, which small and medium-sized enterprises often cannot afford. One of the obstacles to implementing IT in traditional businesses, which are behind in terms of IT, is the lack of basic knowledge on the use of IT in business.

Regarding this topic, the respondents also emphasised that there is not enough data to quantify the effects of applying information technology as a support for sustainability practices.

V - Practice of sustainability reporting in widening countries, potentials, and limitations.

The fifth group of questions was aimed at confirming whether the organisations of the participants have so far reported on sustainable business practices (so-called ESG reporting), what the practice of sustainability reporting in widening countries is, and what the potential and limitations are for sustainability reporting.

The practices of ESG reporting are different in widening countries. In some countries, this practice is a legal obligation only for large companies employing more than 500 workers; in others, it is for those listed on the stock exchanges. This obligation also requires the organisations that are part of international corporations to implement it in a consolidated form for the parent company because

the parent company requires them to do so. Other companies do not have this obligation, which means that the practice of reporting on sustainability is applied by a relatively small number of companies. The respondents agree that reporting is much simpler if the organisations are part of international corporations because these companies implement the criteria and standards that other member companies in Europe do.

When it comes to challenges related to the practice of reporting, it was stated that the legal regulations in this area are imprecise, i.e., that the indicators that should be monitored have not been specified. The respondents also stated that the European directive ESRS (*European Sustainability Reporting Standards*) proclaims the standards that should be reported, the issue of the indicators that should be monitored, as well as the structure of the reports themselves, is still open.

As a limitation for sustainability reporting, the respondent from the financial sector highlighted that there is a lack of commitment to this obligation, that the volume of data can be a challenge for companies, the high cost associated with sustainability reporting, and the lack of an appropriate legal solution for effective regulation.

As an advantage of introducing the practice of reporting on sustainability, the respondents stated that the very fact that it becomes an obligation for companies will require companies to think more about this topic and to identify opportunities for improvements in this area (reduction of electricity and water consumption, improvement of business processes, cost optimisation, impact on the environment, employees, etc.).

Summary:

Bearing in mind the attitudes expressed by the respondents of the focus group on the subject of sustainability and sustainability reporting, below is an **overview of the conclusions and key points** classified by the areas discussed.

I - In the area of environmental sustainability, the key points that were pointed out are as follows:

- It is necessary to use renewable energy sources more.
- It is necessary to work on purifying wastewater and preventing its pollution.
- It is necessary to work on educating young people about the importance of recycling and sustainability from the earliest days.
- The recycling industry faces obstacles, including inadequate waste collection practices.
- Illegal landfills require large-scale recycling projects.
- Banks support renewable energy projects and energy-efficient housing.
- Climate change has positive and negative impacts.

In the area of **economic sustainability**, the key points that were pointed out were:

- Companies should integrate sustainable practices into their business strategies for long-term competitiveness and success.
- Sustainable practices enhance access to financial resources for business development.
- Savings from renewable resources benefit both the environment and financial results.
- Application of sustainability concepts can lead to new business opportunities, especially in the EU market.

- Sustainable practices positively impact a company's image and reputation.
- A lack of recycling infrastructure leads to an increase in recycling costs.
- Some companies avoid eco-taxes by classifying imported devices differently.

In the area of **social sustainability**, the key points are as follows:

- Participants emphasised their companies' commitment to social sustainability,
- Some companies receive certificates confirming their social responsibility efforts, including equality, development, and being a top employer.
- Banks contribute to social responsibility by avoiding financing industries that are not ecologically and socially responsible.
- Increasing investment in green products and issuing green bonds is a trend.

The participants also addressed several challenges such as follows:

- *System of Values*: there is the need for shifting from ego-centric to eco-centric thinking.
- *Legal Regulation*: the clear rules for social responsibility are missing.
- *Measuring Social Impact*: it is more complex to measure social impact (e.g., gender balance and workforce diversity) than measuring environmental impact.

II - Regarding the **sustainability in which the widening countries lags behind the other countries**, the key points are as follows:

- Some counties addressed environmental aspects, while some social aspects.
- All participants stated that investments in environmental sustainability are most often considered a costs.
- The participant stated that legal regulations related to the reduction of polluting emissions and waterwaste either is not adequate developed either not applied.
- There are many bureaucratic obstacles for higher level of sustainability practice implementation and low awareness regarding this topic generally.

III - Regarding the activities of the **circular economy**, the following was concluded:

- Circular economy activities are limited in some widening countries, mainly accessible to large enterprises.
- Implementing circular practices in small and medium enterprises remains difficult.
- Waste collection rates in some widening countries are low (around 20-30%).
- Informal waste pickers often collect more waste than official systems.
- Deposit-refund systems need improvement for better effectiveness.
- There is the need for improving legal solutions for circular economy practices.
- Cooperation among stakeholders should be promoted more.
- Establishing a specialized system for managing specific types of waste is an urgent need.

IV – Regarding **the opportunities for applying IT to support sustainability-based practices**, the following was concluded:

- Artificial intelligence can be used for data reduction, waste sorting (especially in the field of e-recycling), processing large amounts of data, etc.

- IT can be used in the sphere of production automation, optimisation of business processes in the function of energy saving, etc.
- The digitalization of services and mobile banking reduces the need for physical visits to branches and ATMs.
- High IT costs pose challenges for small and medium-sized enterprises.
- Lack of basic IT knowledge limits its adoption in traditional businesses.

V – When it is about **the practice of sustainability reporting in the Republic of Serbia**, the following conclusion is made:

- ESG reporting requirements vary across countries.
- Legal obligations differ based on company size or stock exchange listing; there is no legal obligation for all companies to report on sustainability.
- International corporations often consolidate reporting for their parent companies.
- The legal regulation is imprecise, i.e., the indicators that should be monitored are not specified.
- The introduction of a legal obligation to report on sustainability will contribute to the improvement and wider application of sustainability practices.

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ANNEX

Reviews of the D6.2 Quality Assurance Plan

Review 1

Revier Name: Name and Surname, Acronym of a organisation

Date of review: DD/MM/YYYY

*Reviewer opinion: The deliverable named General opinion: accepted; Comments: No
(150 words)*

Review 2

Revier Name: Name and Surname, Acronym of a organisation

Date of review: DD/MM/YYYY

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(150 words)*